

**Natural Resources documentation for conservation through People Biodiversity
Register(PBR) in Variguntham village, Telangana, India**

Sadam Shivakumar, Syeda Azeem Unnisa*, Vattikoti Praveen, E. Revathi

Department of Environmental Science, Osmania University Hyderabad-500007,

Telangana State, India.

Abstract

The local groups retain traditional wisdom that has been passed down through the years. There are 538 mandals and 130 municipalities in Telangana State. In Telangana State Biodiversity Board (TSBB), has established Biodiversity Management Committees (BMC) in all villages. In People Biodiversity Registers (PBR), locals and technical support organizations document native biodiversity and bio-resources. The village resources, including its socioeconomic, historical, and cultural aspects as well as its natural habitats, are documented by the Biodiversity Management Committee. These habitats include lakes, springs, rare ecological habitat versatility, agro-physiological ecological systems, and ancient distinctive hydrogeological structures made possible by regional methods for managing surface water. The research study of Variguntham village in Telangana, where locals have recorded the bioresources is covered in the article. As a result of the PBR documentation procedure, there are new species identified in communities and agricultural biodiversity. Through PBR four categories have been documented, including 31 type of crops species, 13 type of weeds, 4 types of fruit plants and 13 types of a crop pest. TSBB endeavours to promote historically farmed rice types by giving them a brand identity and recreating ancient customs, etc.

Keywords: Biodiversity management committees(BMC), PBR, Village, Conservation.

1.0 Introduction

The term biodiversity has become a modern buzzword because it is increasingly being regarded as a future resource. Since the beginning of time, the interaction between people and biodiversity has changed. This relationship produces and modifies traditional ecological knowledge and wisdom of local biodiversity. In India, biological diversity is protected via the cooperation of large numbers of people, as many people still rely on it for their daily sustenance. Recognizing this reality, India's Biological Diversity Act of

2002 proposes decentralizing biodiversity management to Panchayat Raj institutions (three-tier councils beginning with village, development block, and district). Municipalities and city corporations that create Biodiversity Management Committees (BMC) will supplement the State Biodiversity Boards (SBM) and the National Biodiversity Authority (NBA). Thus, the only authentic information on the state and dynamics of natural medicinal plant populations, albeit limited to their particular locations, is held by forest produce collectors engaged by pharmaceutical company agents or by folk herbal practitioners. Because successful action can only arise from a solid foundation of knowledge. Because of the vast variance in the distribution and uses of biodiversity from place to place, this documentation is highly local and time specific. The Biological Diversity Act rules refer to such local-level documentation as PBR. It is one of the aspects of the overall "Biodiversity Information System (BIS)" that is being built at the national level, albeit the most original and significant. The local community uses traditional wisdom to protect the biodiversity of the lands for their cultural and spiritual needs. However, no inventory has been created with the participation of people and their traditional knowledge to date [6-7]. Documentation of biodiversity knowledge is relevant in the context of India's Biological Diversity Act, 2002, as well as the provisions of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) for equitable benefit sharing with knowledge holders. To support this goal, the elaborated PBR has been included in the documentation of local biodiversity, relationships, and knowledge of biodiversity in the context of medicinal as well as other uses, their ecological knowledge, and their perceptions of ongoing and desired patterns of biodiversity management [8-10]. Initially, in 1996, a series of PBR was prepared with the assistance of networks of environment-oriented NGOs, and educational institutions at the level of community colleges. With time and the increasing availability and capabilities of current information and communication technology tools, the programme has been perfected to the point where most of the information created may be pooled together and structured with the use of a sensible database management system.

2.0 Study area:

Variguntham is a village in Kulcharam mandal in Medak. Medak district is one among 31 districts and it was formed on October 11,2016 in the state of Telangana.Medak district

headquarters is situated at Sangareddy and spread across 2765 square kilometers and has a population of 7,67,428 as per 2011 Census data. Variguntham is located with the coordinates: 17.9365⁰N, 78.1707⁰E, 210 meters above sea level. The villages geographically occupies total area of 1218 hectares. The non-agricultural area is 22 hectares and irrigated area is 343.5 hectares.

Medak District

Fig:1 Medak district map

Fig.2: Location of Variguntham village

3.0 Methodology:

The basic methodology was to approach the local people directly using individual, and group discussions, and the data was collected as per the PBR Proforma. National

Biodiversity Authority (NBA), New Delhi formats have been undertaken to understand the indigenous knowledge regarding flora, fauna, livelihood options, perceptions, and motivations. The NBA consists of four formats and the data was documented by the below methods.

1. Interviews: Information related to the history of the village, local institutions and decision-making, people landscape aspects, and biodiversity were collected from village chiefs and knowledgeable individuals through personal interviews. Local communities were shown local field guides on various taxa (e.g. birds, mammals, butterflies, and reptiles) and asked to list the species found in their village, their local names and uses, and their current status.

2. Group discussions: It was conducted with village elders and knowledgeable individuals. Discussions were mainly held to validate the information gathered at various levels.

3. Field visits: Field visits were carried out with members of the village, BMC council and local knowledgeable individuals to document the bio-resources of the village. For the fauna survey opportunistic documentation was carried out and species observed were recorded.

4. Village BMC council meetings: The village BMC council meeting was conducted at the village council involving all the stakeholders. The village council members and the village development board members were present at the meeting along with women group members. Village health workers and other officials were also present during the meeting. This meeting helped to understand various issues about the conservation of the conserved area and to identify possible solutions to tackle the problems.

Extensive interviews were conducted by using an interview schedule which consists of both open and closed-ended questionnaires. Group discussions and resource mapping were the other tools used to collect primary data. The secondary data was collected from the reports of the forest department, census data, and reports published by various agencies. The information was collected by visiting the village in person.

1. Primary data collection
2. Secondary data collection
3. Process in PBR Preparation.

3.1 Primary data collection

Primary data is data that is collected by a researcher/data collector from first-hand sources, using methods like surveys or interviews. The primary data for PBR was collected in the prescribed format

Researcher took help of the local people, local leaders, representative of public, Panchayat member, BMC members and related government field level institutes, field officials line department and krishi vigyanan Kendra. The researcher have carried out the checklist of commonly known flora and fauna of the villages consisting of two seasons, the data was collected for one year consisting of two seasons.

3.2 Secondary data collection

Secondary data is the data that have been already published, collected and readily available from other sources. The secondary data was collected as per the requirement of specified formats. The secondary data was collected by researcher. The data was collected during the 2018-2019 from the sources as per the required format. The researcher consulted the office of line departments (Agriculture, forest, horticulture, animal husbandry), Tahsildar office, grampanchayat and revenue office. The scientific data/technical data was collected with help of various departments, University, journals/Research articles/TSBB data banks.

3.3 Process in PBR Preparation

Step1; Interaction with already formed BMC by the TSBB in Variguntham village.

Step2; Sensitization of the public about the study, survey and possible management of the natural resource.

Step3; Interaction with knowledgeable members in the identification and collection of data on biological resources and traditional knowledge.

Step4; Collection of data. Data collection includes a review of literature on the natural resources of the districts, Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) at the village level, household interviews, individual interviews with village leaders and knowledgeable individuals, household heads, key actors of the panchayat raj institutions and NGOs and direct field observations.

Step5; Analysis and validation of data in consultation with the technical support group and BMC.

Step6; Preparation of PBR according to NBA formats.

Step7;Data analysis and report.

4.0 Results and discussion

PBR preparation involves collecting material gathered through field investigations into the PBR document. This same process of field investigation includes the following components, identifying different biodiversity users group, identifying knowledgeable individuals in different aspects of the distribution of biodiversity, interviewing individuals and groups with members representing different user groups, mapping the study site landscape, visiting representative elements of this terrain, and also to document the species that are present in the village as per the people knowledge, according to the NBA Format.

Population composition

According to the 2011 census, the total population of Variguntham Panchayat was 2743, out of which 1334 are males and 1409 are females. This panchayat includes consists of 582 households.

Fig:3 Population

Socio-Economic profile

The village population can be divided into three categories based on their reliance on the local biodiversity: those who depend on agriculture, secondary who depend on wood fuel collectors and cattle grazers, both of which are directly reliant on the biodiversity in the area, and some private and government employees, as well as some drivers, maintenance workers, and other occupations, who depend on the biodiversity in the area indirectly. The village's annual average income varies from 3000 and 8,000.

Figure:7 No.f families engaged in various profession.

Education and literacy:

Within the limits of the this panchayat, there really are three main classes: one elementary, one middle, and one high school. The majority of individuals such as the tribespeople, want to send their children to school since they believe it will assist him escape the impoverished economic situation. Male help compensate 55.02 percent of a neighborhood's literate rate, whereas females compensate 35.34 percent.

Socio-cultural Aspects:

The festivities and religious customs of the villagers show its rich cultural background.

Soil and Water

The Plateau is just where Variguntham is located. It contains a range of soil types, include sandy loams, loamy sands, and sandy clay loams. Mangoes, cotton, maize, groundnuts, paddy, and other fruit and vegetable crops can be grown on these types of soil. The average annual rainfall is 886.9mm.

The main source for drinking water in the towns and villages is aquifer. People living in the majority of village areas think that local access to drinking water is good to excellent (quantity of bore wells: 05, refilling stations: 06, amount of pumping stations: 03, overall volumes of water storage tank: 06, major water tanks: 04, minor storage tanks: 02).

The biodiversity data was collected according to the NBA Format:

The following data on Agrobiodiversity is given in table 2

Table 2. Data collection on Agro Biodiversity of Variguntham village

<u>Crop</u>		<u>Weeds</u>	
<u>Scientific Name</u>	<u>Local Name</u>	<u>Scientific Name</u>	<u>Local Name</u>
<i>Oryza Sativa</i>	Vari	<i>Eragrostis Tenella</i>	Piichi gaddi
<i>Cajanus Cajan</i>	Kandulu	<i>Chloris Barbata</i>	Uppu gaddi
<i>Syzygium Cumini</i>	Alla neredi	<i>Datura Metel</i>	Ummeta
<i>Spinacia Oeracea</i>	Pala Kura	<i>Parthenium Hysterophorus</i>	Vayari bhama
<i>Gossypium Sps</i>	Patti	<i>Achyranthes Aspera</i>	Uthareni
<i>Vigna Radiata</i>	Pesara	<i>Tridax Procumbens</i>	Gaddi chamanti
<i>Manzifera Indica</i>	Mamidi	<i>Cyperus Rotundus</i>	Tunga musta
<i>Phoenix Sylvestris</i>	Eetha	<i>Cynodon Dactylon</i>	Garika
<i>Phyllanthus Emblica</i>	Usiri	<i>Tephrosia Purpurea</i>	Vempalli
<i>Zea Maize</i>	Makka	<i>Solena Heterophylla</i>	Adavi donda
<i>Criticum Velgera</i>	Jonna	<i>Cleome Gynandra</i>	Vaminta
<i>Sorghum Bicolor</i>	Jonna	<i>Phyllanthus Amarus</i>	Nela usari
<i>Zizyphus Jujoba</i>	Regu pandlu	<i>Citrullus Colocynthis</i>	Verri puchakaya
<i>Carica Papaya</i>	Boppai	Total	13
<i>Cocos Nucifera</i>	Kobbari kaya	Fruit Plants	
<i>Tamarindus Indica</i>	Chinta	Scientific name	Local name

<i>Borassus Flabellifer</i>	Tati	<i>Mangifera Indica</i>	Mamidi
<i>Lycopersicum Esculentus</i>	Tameta	<i>Psidium Guajava</i>	Jama
<i>Solanum Melongena</i>	Vankaya	<i>Carica Papaya</i>	Boppai
<i>Luffa Acutangula</i>	Birakaya	<i>Punica Granatum</i>	Daanima
<i>Allium Cepa</i>	Vullipaya	Total	04
<i>Abelmoschus Esculentus</i>	Benda	<u>Pest of Crops</u>	
<i>Moringa Oleifera</i>	Munaga	Scientific name	Local name
<i>Hibiscus Cannabinus</i>	Gongura	<i>Nilaparvata Lugens</i>	Aggi tegulu
<i>Rumex Vesicarius</i>	Chukka kura	<i>Scriphophaga Incertulus</i>	Kandom purugu
<i>Coriandrum Sativum</i>	Kottimera	<i>Nilaparvata Lugens</i>	Dooma
<i>Coccinia Grandis</i>	Dondakaya	<i>Waphalocrosis Medimalis</i>	Aakuchuta purugu
<i>Mentha Spicata</i>	Pudina	<i>PsaraBipuntalis</i>	Akkuannupurugu
<i>Murraya Koenigii</i>	Karvaypaku	<i>Luecinodes</i>	Kandam purugu
<i>Lagenaria Siceraria</i>	Sorakaya	<i>Bemisia Tabaci</i>	Tella domma
		<i>Spodoptera Litura</i>	Ladday purugu
Total	31	<i>Xanthomonas Axonopodis</i>	Akku purugu
		<i>Earis Spp</i>	Machala purugu
		<i>Amrasea Abiguttula</i>	Pacha doma
		<i>Bipolaris Turcicum</i>	Akku purugu
		<i>Meloidogyna Incognita</i>	Veeru purugu
		Total	13

Agro-biodiversity

Agriculture is the backbone of Variguntham's economy. Rainwater collection resources are used by farms for irrigation. A most significant food crop is rice. Additional notable crops are corn, oilseeds, and textiles. A crops from each of the five families: Poaceae, Malvaceae, Fabaceae, Cucurbitaceae, and Solanaceae is presented in Table 2's information regarding agro - ecosystems. Agricultural forms (31 kinds), herbicides (13 kinds), fruit crops (04 kinds), and agricultural insects are indeed the 4 types in agro - ecosystems (13 kinds).

Cissus Vitiginea

*Hyptis
Ipomoea*

*suaveolens
obscura*

Pergularia dae

Table 3 Data Collection on wild plants medicinal species biodiversity of Variguntham Village.

<u>Medicinal plants</u>		<u>Fumigatory Plants</u>	
<u>Scientific Names</u>	<u>Local names</u>	<u>Scientific Names</u>	<u>Local names</u>
<i>Azadirachta Indica</i>	Veepa	<i>Azadirachta Indica</i>	Veepa
<i>Chrysanthemum Sp</i>	Chamanthi	<i>Achyranthes Aspara</i>	Uttareni
<i>Tagetes Erectus</i>	Banthi	<i>Tamarindus Indica</i>	Chinta
<i>Rosa</i>	Gulabi	<i>Ricinus Communis</i>	Aamudam
<i>Jasminum</i>	Mallae	Total	04
<i>Ocimum Sanctum</i>	Tulasi	<u>Timber Plants</u>	
<i>Crossandra Infundibuliformis</i>	Kanakambaram	<u>Scientific Names</u>	<u>Local names</u>
<i>Portulaca Grandiflorum</i>	Table Rosa	<i>Tectona Grandis</i>	Teak
<i>Polianthesus Tuberosa</i>	Sampenga	<i>Tamarindus Indica</i>	Chinta
<i>Cocos Nucifera</i>	Cobbara chettu	<i>Mangifera Indica</i>	Mamidi
<i>Nerium Oleander</i>	Gannaru	<i>Azadirachta Indica</i>	Veepa
<i>Hibiscus Rosa-Sinensis</i>	Mandaram	<i>Ficus Benghalensis</i>	Marri
<i>Phyllanthus Emblica</i>	Vusari	<i>Ficus Religiosa</i>	Raavi
<i>Phoenix Dactylifera</i>	Yeeta	<i>Ecalyptus Globulus</i>	Jamaoil
<i>Borassus Flabellifer</i>	Thati	chettu	
<i>Moringa Oleifera</i>	Munaga	<i>Delonix Regia</i>	Gulmohar
<i>Butea Monosperma</i>	Modhuga	<i>Acacia Nilotica</i>	Tumma
<i>Ficus Venghanensis</i>	Marri	<i>Hardwickia Binata</i>	Vepi
<i>Ficus Glomerata</i>	Medi	<i>Leucaena Luecocephala</i>	Subabul
<i>Ficus Religiosa</i>	Raavi	<i>Butea Monosperma</i>	Moduga
<i>Prosopis Cinereria</i>	Jammi	Total	12
<i>Pithacalobium Dulce</i>	Cheema chinta	<u>Ornamental Plants</u>	<u>Local names</u>
<i>Tamarindus Indica</i>	Chinta	<i>Chrysanthemum Sp</i>	Chamanthi
<i>Tectona Grandis</i>	Teak	<i>Tagetes Erectus</i>	Banthi
<i>Syzygium Cumini</i>	Neeradu	<i>Rosa</i>	Gulabi
<i>Senna Auriculata</i>	Tangedu	<i>Jasminum</i>	Mallae
<i>Phyllanthus Niruri</i>	Nella usiri	<i>Ocimum Sanctum</i>	Tulasi
<i>Tribulus Terrestris</i>	Pallarukaya	<i>C. Infundibuliformis</i>	Kanakambaram
<i>Cissus Quadrangularis</i>	Nallaru	<i>Portulaca Grandiflorum</i>	Table Rosa
<i>Ocimum Tenuiflorum</i>	Tulasi	<i>Polianthesus Tuberosa</i>	Sampenga
<i>Abrus Precatorius</i>	Guruvinda	<i>Cocos Nucifera</i>	Cobbara chettu
<i>Acheranthes Aspera</i>	Uttareni	<i>Nerium Oleander</i>	Gannaru
<i>Aeverta Lalata</i>	Pindi kura	<i>Hibiscus Rosa-Sinensis</i>	Mandaram
<i>Agava Americana</i>	Kalabanda	Total	11
<i>Aloe Vera</i>	Manchi Kalabanda		
<i>Cleome Viscose</i>	Kukka vamintaku		
<i>Datura Metel</i>	Umetha		
<i>Eclitaprostrata</i>	Gunta garage aku		
<i>Tinospora Cordifolia</i>	Tippateega		
<i>Diplocyclos Palmatus</i>	Lingadonda		
<i>Calotropis Gigantea</i>	Jilladu		
<i>Abutilon Indicum</i>	Thuthurabenda		
<i>Dodonaea Viscose</i>	Bandera aku		
<i>Allamanda Cathartica</i>	Allamanda		

<i>Datura Metel</i>	<i>Ummatha</i>	
<i>Hibiscus Rosasinensis</i>	<i>Mandaram</i>	
<i>Ipomoea obscura</i>	<i>Golamadditiga</i>	
<i>Cissusvitiginea</i>	<i>Kuddudinnae</i>	
<i>Pergulariadaemia</i>	<i>Gutaguta,</i>	
<i>Hyptis suaveolens</i>	<i>Peddinguvakoora</i>	
Total no.	50	

majority of the plants belong to

Timber Plants - Meliaceae, Moraceae, Anacardiaceae, Lamiaceae

Medicinal plants - Moraceae, Fabaceae, Arecaceae, Amaranthaceae, Sapindaceae

Ornament plants - Asteraceae, Asparagaceae, Malvaceae

Fumigatory plants - Meliaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Fabaceae family.

Variguntham village high medicinal values plants were found which are

***Ipomoea obscura* (CONVOLVULACEAE)**

For an urgent stomachache, half a teaspoon of leaf extract was given three times in two hours.

***Cissusvitiginea* (VITACEAE)**

Stem bark paste is used topically to wounds for wounds.

***Pergulariadaemia* (ASCLEPIADACEAE)**

For stomachaches, take 3–4 tablespoons of aerial parts extract twice daily.

***Hyptis suaveolens* (LAMIACEAE)**

Invasive weed which spreads in affected regions and open forests.

Extract of leaves (12–15 ml) was consumed three times daily treating snake bites, while leaf decoction was topically as an ointment.

Table 4Data collection on wild relative plant biodiversity of Variguntham village

Trees		Shrubs	
<i>Tamarindus Indicia</i>	<i>Chinta</i>	<i>Heliotropium Indicum</i>	<i>Danti</i>
<i>Ficus Venghanensis</i>	<i>Marri</i>	<i>Senna Auriculata</i>	<i>Tangedu</i>

<i>Syzygium Cuminiin</i>	<i>Neeradu</i>	grass	
<i>Pithacalobium Dulce</i>	<i>Cheema chinta</i>	<i>Cynodon Dactylon</i>	<i>Garika gaddi</i>
<i>Phyllanthus Emblica</i>	<i>Vusari</i>	<i>Desmostachya Bipinnata</i>	<i>Dabha gaddi</i>
<i>Tectona Grandis</i>	<i>Teak</i>	<i>CymbopogonCitratus</i>	<i>Nimma gaddi</i>
<i>Ficus Religiosa</i>	<i>Raavi</i>	<i>Cynodon Dactylon</i>	<i>Garika</i>
<i>Prosopis Cinereria</i>	<i>Jammi</i>	Tubers	
<i>Senna Auriculata</i>	<i>Tangedu</i>	<i>UrgineaIndica</i>	<i>Addaviulli</i>
		<i>Ipomoea Batatas</i>	<i>Moram gadda</i>
Herbs		<i>Maerua Oblongifolia</i>	<i>Bhuchakra gadda</i>
<i>Acalypha Indica</i>	<i>Kuppichettu</i>	<i>Niru Pippali</i>	<i>Gloriosa superba</i>
<i>Leucas Zeylanica</i>	<i>Thummi</i>	Climbers	
<i>Celosia Spicata</i>	<i>Gunugu</i>	<i>Coccinia Grandis</i>	<i>Donda</i>
<i>Agave Americana</i>	<i>Kalabanda</i>	<i>Tinospora Cordifolia</i>	<i>Tippa tiga</i>

Table 5 Data collection on domesticated animal biodiversity of Variguntham village

S No	Mammals		Birds		Reptiles	
	Local name	Scientific name	Local name	scientific name	Local name	scientific name
1	Pilli	<i>Felis Sylvestris Catus</i>	Koodi	Gallus	Frog	<i>Rana hexadactyla</i>
2	Mekalu	<i>Capra Aegagrushircus</i>	Domesticus			
3	Yeddulu/ Aavulu	<i>Bos Taurus</i>			House lizard flaviviridis	<i>Hemidactylus</i>
4	Barrelu	<i>Bos Bubalis</i>				
5	Gorrelu	<i>Ovis Aries</i>				
6	Kukalu	<i>Canus Lepus Familiaris</i>				
Total	6			1		2

Domestic animal biodiversity

Cattle, dogs, and chickens are the animal groups that have been kept under domesticated by a significant section of the people in the Variguntham village clusters for many generations. Goat, sheep, and poultry are usually bought for your meat. Following table

shows those groups within which the majority of farm animals belong: Bovidae, Canidae, and Phasianidae.

There really are three distinct types of cultivated biodiversity. There really are six different types of mammal, single type of bird, and two types species reptile.

Table 6 Various types of biodiversity species in Variguntham village

Agro Biodiversity		Wild biodiversity	
Type	No	Type	No
Crop	31	Shrubs	09
Weed	13	Herbs	04
Fruit Plant	04	Tubers	04
Pest of Crops	13	Grasses	04
		Climbers	02
		Fumigate plant	04
		Timber plants	12
		Medicinal plants	36
		Ornamental plants	04
		Trees	09
Domesticated biodiversity			
Type	No		
Mammals	06		
Birds	01		
Reptiles	01		

A type of wild biodiversity has been named. Shrubs species include 9, Herbs 4, Tubers 4, Grasses 4, Climbers 2, Fumigate Plants 4, Timber Plants 12, Medicinal Plants 50, Ornamental Plants 4, and Trees Among these, there are 40 Shrub species.

Wild animal biodiversity

In additional the monkeys and wild pigs, surrounding forests are habitat to various snake species, reptiles, birds, fox, and other animals that damage agriculture..

Conclusions

PBR contains in-depth knowledge and information on regional bio - resources, as well as conventional knowledge about such materials' uses in medical as well as other fields. So order to encourage livelihood dependent upon diversity and contribute towards conservation of biodiversity, PBR documentation is required. Of that kind information

might very well also serve as a benchmark for integrating local issues in to the making plans, trying to identify indigenous knowledge owners and describing their expert knowledge, trying to regulate direct exposure to bio - resources, and trying to educate a next production concerning conventional conservation practices as well as there own effectiveness inside the actual life.

References

1 The sustainability revolution: Portrait of a paradigm shift

- [1]. Biological Diversity Act 2002, Ministry of Environment and Forests. Government of India
- [2]. Rautaray, O. P., Pradhan, R. N., Behera, P., & Sahu, H. K. (2014). People's biodiversity register [PBR]: a community based new venture in Odisha to document natural resources. *Environ Ecol Res*, 2(8), 285-290.
- [3]. Gadgil, M., & Seshagiri Rao, P. R. (1998). *Nurturing biodiversity*. Centre for Environment Education.
- [4]. Gadgil, M., Seshagiri Rao, P. R., Utkarsh, G., Pramod, P., & Chhatre, A. (2000). New meanings for old knowledge: the people's biodiversity registers program. *Ecological Applications*, 10(5), 1307-1317.
- [5]. Gadgil, M., Achar, K. P., Bhat, H., Bhat, P. R., Deshmukh, S., & Dolke, A. (2006). Ecology is for the people: a methodology manual for people's biodiversity register. *Centre for Ecological Sciences/Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore*. 233p.
- [6]. Gupta, A. K., & Sinha, R. (2002). Contested Domains, Fragmented Spaces: rights, responsibilities and rewards for conserving biodiversity and associated knowledge systems. *Traditional ecological knowledge for managing biosphere reserves in south and central Asia*, 161-181.
- [7]. Gupta, A. K. (1999). Conserving biodiversity and rewarding associated knowledge and innovation systems: Honey bee perspective. Bern: Paper presented at the World Trade Forum.
- [8]. Hansen, S. A., & VanFleet, J. W. (2003). A handbook on issues and options for traditional knowledge holders in protecting their intellectual property and maintaining biological diversity. *Washington, DC*.

- [9]. Ministry of Environment and Forest notification The Gazette of India April, 15, 2004.
- [10]. People's Biodiversity Register: Documenting biodiversity for natural resource management Gokhale Y.1*, Gadgil M.2, Achar K. P.2 , Gunaga S.2 , Heda N.2 , Nayak M.2, Patgar S2 ., Pandharipande K.3, Mohan H.4, Dolke Y5 ., Gurnule K. Perspectives on Biodiversity - A Vision for Mega diverse Countries. Published by Ministry of Environment and Forests, Govt. of India. 2005. Pg.375-396.
- [11]. Berkes F, Kislalioglu M, Folke C, Godgil M 1998. Exploring the basic ecological unit: Ecosystem-like concepts in traditional societies. *Ecosystems*, 1: 409-415.
- [12]. Bhattacharya P, Hayat SF 2004. Sustainable NTFP management for rural development: A case study from Madhya Pradesh. *International Forestry Review*, 6(2): 161-168.
- [13]. Chambers R 1983. *Rural Development: Putting the Last First*. London: Orient Longman. Chandrashekara UM, Sankar S 1998. Ecology and management of sacred groves in Kerala, India. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 112: 165-177.
- [14]. Dutfield G 1999. Intellectual Property Rights and Plant Genetic Resources with Particular Reference to Seeds and Plant Varieties.
- [15]. Gland: IUCN. Forest Resources. Online (Retrieved on May 3, 2006).
- [16]. Gadgil M 1982. Conservation of India's living resources through biosphere reserves. *Current Science*, 51: 547- 550.
- [17]. Gadgil M 2006. *Methodology Manual for People's Biodiversity Register*. Chennai: National Biodiversity Authority.

- [18]. Gadgil Madhav “Srushtigyaan, A Methodology Manual for Documenting People’s Priorities for Biodiversity and Conservation.” Online (Retrieved on December 22, 2005). Gadgil M, Berkes F 1991. Traditional resource management systems, *Resource Management and Optimisation*, 18 (3 4): 27 141.
- [19]. Gadgil M, Berkes F, Folke C 1993. Indigenous knowledge for biodiversity conservation, *Ambio*, 22: 151 156. Ghate Utkarsh “Documenting Traditional Knowledge: People’s Biodiversity Register.” Online (Retrieved on December 21, 2005).
- [20]. Grimmett R, Inskipp C, Inskipp T 2001. *Birds of Indian Subcontinent*. Singapore: Oxford University Press. Kanowski PJ, Gilmour DA, Margules CR, Potter CS 1999. *International Forest Conservation: Protected Areas and Beyond*. Canberra: Commonwealth of Australia. Kunte, K. 2000. *Butterflies of Peninsular India*. Hyderabad: Universities Press.
- [21]. Malhotra Kailash C, Gokhle Yogesh 2007. *Sacred Groves in India an Overview*. Bhopal: Indira Gandhi Rashtriya Manav Sangrahalaya, and New Delhi: Aryan Books International.
- [22]. Malhotra KC, Bhattacharya Prodyut 2010. *Forest and Livelihood*. Hyderabad: CESS.
- [23]. Martin GJ 1995. *Ethnobotany: A Method’s Manual*. London: Chapman and Hall. MoEF 2009. *India’s Fourth National Report to the Convention on Biological Diversity*. New Delhi: MoEF, Govt. of India.
- [24]. Pandey DN “Traditional Knowledge Systems for Biodiversity Conservation.” Online (Retrieved on December 23, 2005).

- [25].Poffenberger M, Pandey DN 2001. Indic traditional in forestry: a case of integration of Indigenous knowledge with formal forestry. International Conference on Indigenous India Traditions in Forestry, Lessons for Contemporary Sustainable Forest Management, 8-10 Feb., 2001, Bhopal
- [26].Protection of Biodiversity and Traditional Knowledge-The Indian Experience. Online (Retrieved on May 3, 2006).
- [27].Sharma BD 1997. Tide Turned: The Making of Self Rule in the First Central Law in the Wake of Bhuria Committee Report. New Delhi:
- [28].Sahayog Pustak Parivar. Soils of the State. Online (Retrieved on May 5, 2006)